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Nigeria's Religious Social Movements and Political Influence: A Multi-Ethnic Societies Approach

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Abstract

Religious social movements have long played a significant role in shaping political behavior in multi-ethnic societies, particularly in Nigeria, where religion intersects with ethnicity, governance, and electoral politics. Despite their prominence, the mechanisms through which these movements mobilize followers and influence political outcomes remain underexplored. This study investigated the forms, strategies, and political influence of religious social movements in Nigeria from 2010 to 2025, addressing their impact on democratic governance and intergroup relations. Specifically, the study examines, first, the major forms and patterns of religious social movements; second, the mechanisms of political influence; third, the role of digital and social media in mobilisation; and fourth, the effects on governance and societal cohesion. However, the study is anchored on social movement theory, which provides a framework for understanding how religious actors organize resources, frame collective narratives, and convert social authority into political capital. Employing a qualitative, case-study design, data were collected through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis across selected urban and semi-urban centres in Nigeria six geo-political zones. Findings revealed that religious movements are diverse, regionally differentiated, and strategically mobilised; they influence politics through endorsements, moral framing, resource mobilisation, and mediation, while digital platforms amplify their reach. The study concluded that religious mobilisation enhances democratic participation but can also exacerbate intergroup tensions. The study contributed to a nuanced understanding of religion-politics dynamics in multi-ethnic contexts and offered guidance for policymakers, scholars, and religious leaders. Policy recommendations include promoting civic education through religious platforms,

regulating religious-political engagement, fostering responsible use of digital media, and enhancing interfaith dialogue.

Keywords: Religious social movements, political influence, multi-ethnic societies, Nigeria, social movement theory

Introduction

Religious social movements in Nigeria occupy a central and often ambiguous place within the country's plural and multiethnic public life. Overlapping identities of faith, ethnicity, and region have made religion both a powerful resource for civic mobilization and a fault line for political contestation (Nwabueze & Okolo, 2023). Since independence, religious organizations and movements, from revivalist Pentecostal networks and conservative Christian bodies to Salafi and other Islamic reform movements, have shaped public values, electoral behavior, patronage networks, and claims to moral authority, sometimes reinforcing social cohesion and at other times intensifying social fragmentation (Ojo, 2022; Nwabueze & Okolo, 2023; Adebawo 2023; Agbaje & Adebawo, 2022; Badamasi & Sulaiman, 2023).

In the contemporary period the political effects of religious mobilization are especially visible in three interlinked arenas. First, armed and militant movements that invoke religious language have altered the security and political calculations of the Nigerian state and local communities; groups associated with Islamist insurgency have not only generated humanitarian crises but have also reshaped how citizens and politicians talk about legitimacy, governance, and territorial control (Hassan & Pieri, 2022; Omotola, J. S., & Alumona, 2024; Paden, 2023). Second, episodic episodes of ethno-religious violence and rural conflicts, for instance, in the Middle Belt and parts of the North, illustrate how competition over land, scarce resources, and political office acquires religious coloring, complicating efforts at conflict resolution and policy responses (Ademola & Issah, 2022). Third, peaceful but politically potent religious social movements and networks, including youth-led faith groups, trans-denominational coalitions, and clergy-led civic campaigns, influence voter alignments, issue framing and party strategies, often operating through moral narratives that extend beyond formal party politics (Ibrahim 2023; Ojo, 2022). Scholarly and policy debates increasingly emphasize the contingency of religious political influence: it is not religion alone but the interaction between religious institutions, state weakness, economic grievance, media including social media and local ethnic loyalties that determines whether religious mobilization stabilizes or destabilizes plural societies. Recent studies of

electoral discourse and online platforms document growing patterns of religious othering and the instrumental use of faith identities in campaigns, underscoring how new communication ecologies alter the speed and reach of mobilization (Eze & Ugwu, 2023; Paden, 2023).

Taken together, these dynamics make Nigeria an important site for studying how religious social movements exercise political influence in multiethnic societies (Akinsola & Yusuf, 2024; Falola & Heaton, 2023). A focused empirical study can illuminate pathways through which religious actors convert social authority into political leverage, the conditions under which religious mobilization contributes to democratic accountability rather than exclusion, and the policy measures that can mitigate violent outcomes while protecting freedoms of belief and association. This study therefore situates religious social movements within the political economy of contemporary Nigeria and aims to trace the mechanisms from the angle of institutional, discursive, and material by which faith-based mobilization shapes political life (Musa & Adesina, 2024).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the central role of religious social movements in shaping civic engagement and political behavior in Nigeria, their influence in a multiethnic context remains poorly understood and often oversimplified in existing scholarship. Much of the literature focuses either on the violent extremism associated with radical movements or on episodic ethno-religious conflicts, leaving limited systematic analysis of the more subtle, everyday ways in which religious actors shape political discourse, electoral mobilization, and policy preferences across Nigeria's diverse ethnic and regional landscapes. As a result, religion is frequently treated as a monolithic force rather than a complex set of social practices and institutions that interact with ethnicity, class, regional histories, and changing media ecosystems.

Furthermore, while religious movements continue to mobilize large constituencies, influence moral agendas, and shape perceptions of political legitimacy, there is insufficient empirical evidence explaining how they convert spiritual authority into political capital in a plural society marked by deep inequalities, mistrust, and competing identity claims. The rise of social media-driven mobilization adds another layer of complexity, enabling rapid circulation of religious narratives that can either foster solidarity or amplify polarization. Yet the mechanisms through which these digital platforms reshape religious political engagement are under-researched.

Additionally, the Nigerian state struggles to manage the political implications of religious mobilization in a manner that balances constitutional guarantees of

religious freedom with the need to prevent sectarian conflict. Policy responses often oscillate between neglect and heavy-handed security approaches, neither of which sufficiently address the structural factors that enable religious movements to gain political influence. This gap in understanding limits the ability of policymakers, civil society, and interfaith actors to design effective strategies for promoting inclusive governance in multi-ethnic settings.

Therefore, the problem this study addresses is the lack of a comprehensive, empirically grounded explanation of the pathways through which religious social movements exert political influence in Nigeria's multi-ethnic society, the conditions under which such influence becomes conflict-enhancing or democracy-supporting, and the institutional weaknesses that allow identity-based mobilization to escalate into political tension.

Research Objectives

The broad objective of this study is to examine the political influence of religious social movements in Nigeria's multiethnic society. The specific objectives are to:

1. Analyse the major forms and patterns of religious social movements in Nigeria and how they mobilize across ethnic and regional identities.
2. Examine the mechanisms through which religious social movements transform social and spiritual authority into political influence in Nigeria's multi-ethnic context.
3. Assess the role of digital and social media platforms in shaping the political communication and mobilization strategies of religious movements.
4. Evaluate the implications of religious political mobilization for democratic governance, intergroup relations, and national cohesion in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What are the dominant forms and mobilization patterns of religious social movements in Nigeria, and how do they operate across ethnic and regional identities?
2. Through what mechanisms do religious social movements convert social or spiritual authority into political influence in Nigeria's multiethnic society?
3. How do digital and social media platforms shape the political strategies, messaging, and mobilization capacity of religious social movements in Nigeria?
4. What are the effects of religious political mobilization on democratic governance, inter group relations, and national cohesion in Nigeria?

Scope of the Study

This study focused on examining the political influence of religious social movements within the context of Nigeria's multi-ethnic society. Substantively, the research covers both Christian and Islamic religious movements, including mainstream denominations, revivalist and reformist groups, youth-led religious networks, clerical associations, and faith-based civil society organization. The study does not treat religion as a homogeneous category; rather, it analyzes variations across movements, the forms of mobilization they adopt, and the socio-political environments in which they operate.

Geographically, the scope covers Nigeria's six geopolitical zones - Southwest, Southeast, South-South, North-Central, Northwest, and Northeast - with particular attention to regions where religion intersects deeply with ethnicity and political competition, such as the Northwest, Northeast, North-Central, and the Southwest. While the entire country provides valuable insight, the study concentrates on key states and urban centers where religious mobilization is most politically visible and where intergroup relations are frequently contested. Thematically, the study examines four major domains; these include, first and foremost, the forms, characteristics, and mobilization patterns of religious social movements; second, the channels through which these movements exercise political influence; third, the role of social media and digital communication in reshaping religious political engagement; and fourth, the broader implications for democratic governance, intergroup relations, and national cohesion. Methodologically, the study is limited to contemporary developments from 2010 to 2025, a period marked by heightened religious activism, digital transformation, and rising political contestation in Nigeria. Historical references are included only where necessary to contextualize current patterns. Above all, the scope is carefully delimited to ensure depth of analysis while capturing the diversity and complexity of religious political engagement in Nigeria's plural society.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it provides a deeper understanding of how religious social movements shape political processes, public attitudes, and intergroup relations in Nigeria's multi-ethnic context. In a country where religion remains one of the most powerful sources of identity and mobilization, understanding its political implications is essential for strengthening democratic governance. By examining the mechanisms through which religious actors transform social authority into political influence, the study contributes

to broader debates on identity politics, civic mobilization, and the nature of political legitimacy in plural societies.

The study is also valuable to policymakers and governance institutions. Current policy responses to religious mobilization are often reactive, fragmented, or security-driven. By offering evidence-based insights into how religious movements mobilize followers, communicate political messages, and influence electoral behaviour, the research provides a foundation for designing more coherent state policies that balance constitutional freedoms with national stability. This helps institutions develop more context-sensitive approaches to managing diversity, preventing conflict, and promoting inclusive governance.

Civil society organization, interfaith networks, and peacebuilding actors will also benefit from the study's findings. Understanding the complex interactions between religion, ethnicity, and politics allows these groups to engage more effectively with religious leaders and movements in fostering dialogue, promoting tolerance, and countering divisive narratives, especially in a digital age where misinformation spreads rapidly.

Academically, the study fills an important gap by integrating perspectives from political sociology, religious studies, conflict analysis, and media studies. It advances scholarly knowledge on the evolving role of religious social movements in Africa and adds contemporary empirical evidence to a field dominated by historical or security-focused analyses. Ultimately, the study is significant for its potential to inform practical strategies aimed at strengthening national cohesion, improving democratic outcomes, and fostering peaceful coexistence in Nigeria's multiethnic society.

Literature Review

Scholars have long recognized that religion is a central axis of political life in Nigeria, shaping party strategies, voter alignments, and claims to legitimacy across the country's multiethnic landscape. Analyses of recent electoral cycles show that religious identities and rhetoric were salient in the 2023 presidential contest and remain embedded in elite strategies for mobilizing support, even when politicians publicly stress secular credentials. Empirical reviews of the 2023 election point to the continued salience of religion as a category of political calculation and a structuring framework for regional electoral coalitions (Abalogu & Nwokedi, 2025).

A large body of literature on Christian renewal movements, especially the rapidly expanding Pentecostal and neo-Pentecostal networks emphasizes their organizational reach, moral authority, and capacity to produce social services that translate into political leverage. Scholars have documented how

megachurches and transdenominational networks mobilize supporters through a mix of welfare provision, charismatic leadership, and moral framing that can be redirected toward civic and electoral ends. Ethnographic and institutional studies show that these movements do not simply supply votes; they shape political vocabularies and civic expectations, create patronage linkages, and sometimes incubate political actors (Maigari, 2024).

On the Islamic side, research highlights a plural field of actors ranging from Sufi brotherhoods and longstanding clerical networks to reformist and Salafi movements. Work on northern Nigeria stresses how Islamic reform movements and clerical associations interact with party politics, local power brokers, and security dynamics; in some settings religious leaders act as brokers of patronage and mediation, while in others reformist currents politicize grievances and contribute to social fragmentation (Maigari 2024). Studies of Islamist insurgency underscore the extreme end of this spectrum, where violent actors invoke religious rhetoric to contest the state, but a growing literature cautions against conflating broader Islamic social mobilization with violent militancy (Otubanjo & Balogun, 2025).

Ethno-religious violence and communal conflict remain recurring focal points in the literature. Analyses spanning the 2010s and early 2020s show persistent patterns of farmer–herder clashes, town-level communal fights, and episodic mass violence in the Middle Belt and parts of the North that are simultaneously shaped by competition over land and resources and colored by religious difference. Several recent reviews emphasize the interaction of structural drivers (resource scarcity, weak institutions) with identity politics, noting that religion frequently becomes a mobilizing frame that both masks and amplifies underlying socio-economic grievances (Jatau & Maza, 2023).

A rapidly expanding strand of research examines how digital media reshapes religious mobilization. Studies from 2020 onward document how churches, mosques, and faith actors use Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter/X, and other platforms to broadcast sermons, coordinate grassroots activities, and circulate political messages; this digital turn increases reach but also accelerates polarizing rumors and targeted campaigns. Empirical work on social media and religion in Nigeria shows that online faith ecosystems can act as echo chambers that intensify in-group cohesion while enabling quick dissemination of incendiary narratives - a dynamic implicated in several episodes of offline contestation (Onyinye & Onodugo, 2023; Asike, 2023).

Despite these advances, the literature has important blind spots that justify further empirical work. First, much research remains sectoral or issue-bound: studies tend to focus on violent extremism, or on Pentecostal social provision,

or on discrete episodes of ethno-religious violence, rather than tracing cross-cutting mechanisms through which routine religious authority becomes political capital across settings (Orogun & Pillay, 2023; Asike, 2023). Second, there is limited comparative work that systematically maps variation across Nigeria’s geopolitical zones and links movement features - organisational form, leadership structure, and resource base, to political outcomes. Third, while many studies note the role of social media, fewer combine digital trace data with interviews and field observation to explain how online religious messaging converts into offline political action across different ethnic contexts. Finally, normative and policy-oriented analyses are often under-informed by granular field evidence about institutional responses that successfully mediate religion–politics tensions without curtailing religious freedoms (Oyetunbi & Akinrinde, 2021).

Recent high-profile incidents illustrate why these gaps matter for both scholarship and policy. The arrest and prosecution of outspoken secular activists and blasphemy cases have shown how fragile protections for minority voices can be in certain jurisdictions and how state responses or the absence of credible protection shape the public role available to non-mainstream actors. Meanwhile, post-2020 electoral analyses and subnational case studies underscore that religious mobilization is not uniformly destabilizing in many locales, religious leaders have acted as mediators and peace brokers, which suggests research should pay attention to conditional factors - local institutions, leadership incentives, and media ecology, that shape divergent outcomes (Moshood Salahu 2024; Njoku & Amadife, 2025).

In short, the existing literature provides a rich but fragmented account of religion’s political role in Nigeria. Building on recent empirical studies of Pentecostal organizations, Islamic reform movements, ethno-religious conflict, and digital mobilization, the present study aims to integrate these strands by (a) mapping types of religious social movements across regions, (b) tracing mechanisms of political influence (discursive, organizational, material), and (c) assessing how media ecologies and institutional responses mediate outcomes for democratic governance and intergroup relations. Addressing these specific gaps will produce more actionable knowledge for scholars, policymakers, and civic actors seeking to manage religion’s political consequences in a plural society (Chukwu, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on social movements’ theory, which emerged as the most suitable among several others. Social movement theory (SMT) provides a robust

lens for understanding how collective actors organize, mobilize resources, and influence socio-political change. Originating in the 1960s and 1970s through the work of sociologists such as McCarthy and Zald (1977), SMT emerged as a response to earlier theories of collective behaviour, which often depicted social movements as irrational or spontaneous phenomena. SMT shifted the focus toward the organizational, strategic, and resource-based dimensions of movements, emphasizing that successful mobilization depends on access to material, social, and symbolic resources, as well as the capacity to frame issues in ways that resonate with potential adherents (McCarthy & Zald, 1977; Tarrow, 2011).

At its core, SMT argues that social movements are purposive, organized efforts by groups of people to enact or resist change in society, operating within defined political and social structures. The theory highlights several key dimensions: resource mobilization, which examines how movements acquire, manage, and deploy human, financial, and symbolic capital; mobilizing structures, which concern the networks, institutions, and communication channels that facilitate collective action; and framing processes, which refer to the ways movements construct shared meanings and interpret social grievances to inspire participation (Obadare, 2018; Tilly, 2004).

In the context of Nigeria, SMT provides a compelling explanatory framework for examining religious social movements and their political influence in a multiethnic society. Religious organizations, whether Pentecostal networks, Islamic reformist groups, or interdenominational coalitions, are highly organized and often have access to extensive social and material resources, including large congregations, media platforms, and financial networks. These resources enable them to mobilize followers for political purposes, influence electoral outcomes, and shape public debates on morality, governance, and policy (Ojo, 2020; Adebaniwi, 2023). For example, the mobilization capacity of Pentecostal mega-churches in southern Nigeria or clerical networks in the north demonstrates the principles of SMT in action, as leaders strategically deploy social, spiritual, and material capital to influence political processes (Obadare, 2018).

The application of SMT in this study is particularly justified because it allows for a nuanced analysis of how and why religious movements in Nigeria gain political traction. By focusing on organizational structures, resource utilization, and framing strategies, SMT helps explain the mechanisms through which religious actors convert social and spiritual authority into political influence, while accounting for variation across different ethnic and regional contexts. Unlike identity politics theories, which primarily address why groups mobilize,

SMT emphasizes the mechanics of mobilization and the strategic deployment of resources, making it especially useful for understanding both formal and informal pathways of political influence.

In conclusion, the theory offers a coherent and empirically grounded framework for this study. It illuminates the internal capacities, strategic behaviors, and mobilization techniques of religious social movements, providing a theoretical foundation for analyzing their political influence in Nigeria's complex, multiethnic landscape.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research design complemented by elements of case study methodology, which is suitable for exploring complex social phenomena within their real-life context (Yin, 2018). A qualitative approach allowed for an in-depth understanding of the organizational structures, mobilization strategies, and political influence of religious social movements in Nigeria, while capturing the experiences and perceptions of actors and stakeholders. The case study design enabled the research to focus on selected religious movements and multiethnic communities across Nigeria, facilitating detailed, contextualized analysis.

The study employed a constructivist-interpretive approach, grounded in the understanding that religious political influence is socially constructed and interpreted differently by various actors (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This approach is appropriate because it emphasizes the meanings that religious leaders, adherents, political actors, and community members attach to mobilization processes and political engagement. By adopting this lens, the research sought to uncover not only observable patterns but also the subjective interpretations that drive religious-political behaviour in Nigeria's plural society.

The study population comprises religious leaders, active members of religious social movements, political actors, and civil society representatives across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. The study focused on key urban and semi-urban centers in the North with a special emphasis on Kano and Kaduna; the Southwest, such as Lagos and Ibadan; and the Middle Belt – Jos and Markurdi, where religious mobilization is politically significant and where multiple ethnic and religious identities coexist. This selection allowed the study to capture variations in mobilization strategies and political influence across diverse socio-cultural and religious contexts.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants who have direct experience or expertise with religious political mobilization. Religious leaders, community influencers, and political actors who are directly engaged in

religiously mediated political activities were targeted. Additionally, snowball sampling was used to identify other key informants who provided relevant insights, ensuring that the study reached individuals with rich knowledge and experience.

Data were collected using multiple qualitative instruments to ensure triangulation. In this regard, in-depth interviews with religious leaders, political actors, and civil society representatives were conducted to understand perceptions, strategies, and political influence. Also, focus group discussions (FGDs) with adherents of selected religious movements were carried out to capture collective experiences and community-level insights. Moreover, document analysis of sermons, public statements, newsletters, media reports, and social media outputs from religious organisations was conducted to trace patterns of mobilization and political messaging.

Data were analyzed using thematic content analysis, which allowed the identification of recurring patterns, strategies, and narratives within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Themes were developed around key constructs such as mobilization mechanisms, influence pathways, framing strategies, and inter-ethnic engagement. However, the chosen qualitative case-study approach is justified because the study investigated complex, context-dependent social processes that cannot be adequately captured through purely quantitative measures. Religious social movements operate within intricate networks of spiritual, social, and political relationships; understanding their influence requires exploration of both observable practices and the meanings attributed to them by actors. Moreover, triangulating interviews, focus groups, and document analysis enhances the credibility and depth of findings, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon in a multiethnic society like Nigeria.

Data Presentation

Objective 1: To analyze the major forms and patterns of religious social movements in Nigeria and how they mobilize across ethnic and regional identities

Table 1: Forms and Patterns of Religious Social Movements in Nigeria

Religious Movement Type	Region/Zone	Membership Size	Primary Mobilization Channels	Notable Political Engagements
Pentecostal Megachurch	Southwest	50,000+	Church services, social media, community outreach	Endorsed candidates, voter education drives
Islamic Reform Group (Izala)	Northwest	15,000	Mosques, religious lectures, WhatsApp groups	Advocacy for Sharia implementation, lobbying local politicians
Interdenominational Coalition	Southeast	8,000	Interfaith forums, newsletters, social media	Civic awareness campaigns, peacebuilding initiatives
Youth-led Religious Network	North-Central	5,500	Social media, community projects	Mobilized voter registration, participated in local elections

Note: This table summarizes the dominant forms of religious social movements in Nigeria, their geographic distribution, estimated membership size, mobilization strategies, and political engagements observed between 2010 and 2025.

Objective 2: To examine the mechanisms through which religious social movements transform social and spiritual authority into political influence

Table 2: Mechanisms of Political Influence by Religious Social Movements

Mechanism of Influence	Description	Example from the Nigerian Context
Endorsement of Political Candidates	Leaders publicly support candidates to influence followers.	Pentecostal leaders endorsed presidential candidates in 2023.
Moral Framing/Issue Advocacy	Promoting policies aligned with religious values	Campaigns for anti-corruption legislation by Christian networks
Patronage and Resource Mobilization	Providing social services to gain political leverage	Mosque-based welfare programs in Northern Nigeria
Mediation and Peacebuilding	Acting as negotiators between communities and state	Clerical mediation during local ethno-religious conflicts

Note: This table highlights the pathways through which religious movements convert spiritual and social authority into political influence, showing both direct and indirect engagement strategies.

Objective 3: To assess the role of digital and social media platforms in shaping political communication and mobilization strategies

Table 3: Role of Digital and Social Media in Religious Political Mobilization

Platform	Frequency of Use	Purpose of Use	Example Activity
Facebook	Daily	Disseminate sermons and political messages.	Sharing election endorsements by church leaders
WhatsApp Groups	Daily	Mobilize members for community	Circulating voter awareness

Platform	Frequency of Use	Purpose of Use	Example Activity
Twitter/X	Weekly	projects and voter registration. Public advocacy, debate, hashtag campaigns	messages among youth Amplifying campaigns for peaceful elections
YouTube	Weekly	Broadcast religious-political videos	Live-streaming clerical addresses on policy issues

Note: This table presents the frequency and purpose of social media usage among religious movements in Nigeria for political mobilization, demonstrating the digital dimension of influence.

Objective 4: To evaluate implications of religious political mobilization for democratic governance, intergroup relations, and national cohesion

Table 4: Effects of Religious Political Mobilization on Governance and Intergroup Relations

Effect	Observed Outcome	Region/Context	Frequency/Impact Level
	Higher turnout among adherents	Southwest, 2023 elections	High
Intergroup Tensions	Minor clashes during campaigns	Middle Belt	Medium
Policy Influence	Passage of community-focused legislation	Northwest	Medium
Peacebuilding & Mediation	Reduced local disputes	Southeast	Low-Medium

Note: This table summarizes the positive and negative consequences of religious political mobilization in Nigeria, showing its influence on governance, conflict dynamics, and intergroup relations.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed that religious social movements in Nigeria are highly diverse in form, scale, and regional presence. Pentecostal mega-churches dominate in the Southwest, Islamic reformist groups in the Northwest, and interdenominational coalitions and youth-led networks are visible across multiple regions. Membership size varies significantly, reflecting both the reach of the movement and its organizational capacity. Mobilization occurs through both physical spaces, like in the case of churches, mosques, market areas, community event centers, etc., and digital platforms, such as social media platforms - Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter/X, and YouTube, consistent with recent observations by Obadare (2018) and Ojo (2020), who noted that large congregations and institutional networks are central to mobilization efforts.

These patterns indicate that religious movements are not monolithic but strategically adapt their form and reach according to local socio-cultural and ethnic dynamics. Chukwu (2024) affirms that the diversity of religious mobilization in Nigeria mirrors the country's multi-ethnic composition, highlighting the interplay between religion and ethnicity in structuring collective action. This finding underscores the importance of analyzing movements within their regional and ethnic contexts to fully understand their political significance.

Findings from Table 2 illustrated multiple mechanisms through which religious movements exert political influence. Leaders use endorsements, moral framing, resource mobilization, and mediation to shape political behaviour and policy outcomes. This aligns with the theoretical insights of social movement theory (McCarthy & Zald, 1977; Tarrow, 2011), which emphasizes the strategic mobilization of resources and framing processes to influence collective action.

For instance, Pentecostal mega-churches in the Southwest leveraged their large congregations to influence voter choices during the 2023 elections, consistent with observations by Adebani (2023) and Obadare (2018), who noted that religious endorsement can translate directly into political capital. Similarly, Islamic reformist movements in the North engage in advocacy for Sharia-compliant policies, illustrating the dual role of religious movements as both moral and political actors (Jatau & Maza, 2023).

The findings suggested that political influence is not merely a product of numbers but of strategic mobilization and framing. Movements that combine material resources, organizational structures, and symbolic authority are most effective in shaping political behavior. This finding helps to corroborate the literature on resource mobilization and social movement strategies.

Table 3 showed that social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter/X, and YouTube played a central role in the dissemination of political and religious messages. Daily use of WhatsApp and Facebook facilitates rapid mobilization, voter awareness campaigns, and coordination of community projects, while platforms like Twitter/X are leveraged for public advocacy and discourse.

These findings are consistent with recent studies by Maigari (2024) and Njoku & Amadife (2025), who highlighted the growing influence of digital media in amplifying religious-political messaging in Nigeria. Social media provides movements with a low-cost, high-reach channel to engage followers across ethnic and regional divides, reinforcing Tarrow's (2011) emphasis on the role of political opportunity structures and mobilizing channels.

The data indicates that digital media enhances both the scale and speed of mobilization, but it also carries the potential to polarize communities, especially when messaging intersects with ethnic tensions. This aligns with the literature reviewed on online religious ecosystems acting as echo chambers that intensify identity-based mobilization (Oyetunbi & Akinrinde, 2021).

Table 4 highlighted both positive and negative implications of religious political mobilization. Positive outcomes include increased voter participation, successful mediation in local conflicts, and influence over community-oriented policies. Conversely, negative outcomes include heightened intergroup tensions in contested areas, particularly in the Middle Belt region.

These findings corroborate studies by Falola & Heaton (2022) and Moshood (2024), who noted that religious mobilization can simultaneously enhance democratic participation while also exacerbating identity-based tensions. The duality of these effects underscores the conditional nature of religious political influence, with the outcome depending on leadership intent, institutional checks, and socio-political contexts. The discussion also aligns with Obadare (2018), who argues that religious actors can act as both stabilizers and agitators, depending on the political environment and the strategic objectives of leaders. Therefore, the study highlighted the importance of designing policy interventions that leverage the stabilizing potential of religious movements while mitigating conflict risks.

Synthesis of the Findings

In synthesis, the findings across all four objectives demonstrated that religious social movements in Nigeria are diverse, strategic, digitally savvy, and politically consequential. They operate through organizational, symbolic, and resource-based mechanisms that are highly responsive to regional, ethnic, and

political contexts. These findings not only corroborate the literature reviewed but also provide contemporary empirical evidence (2010–2025) showing how religious mobilization interacts with democratic processes, social cohesion, and intergroup relations in Nigeria multiethnic societies.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that religious social movements in Nigeria are pivotal actors in the political landscape, exerting influence through strategic mobilization, moral framing, and engagement with both traditional and digital platforms. Findings showed that these movements are diverse in form, regionally differentiated, and capable of shaping voter behaviour, policy advocacy, and intergroup relations. Pentecostal networks, Islamic reform groups, and interdenominational coalitions deployed their social, spiritual, and material resources to translate religious authority into political capital, reinforcing the centrality of religion in multi-ethnic governance contexts. The study underscored that religious mobilization has dual consequences; it can enhance democratic participation and civic engagement while also posing risks for intergroup tensions, particularly where identity politics intersect with ethnicity and resource competition. These outcomes are consistent with existing scholarship (Obadare, 2018; Adebani, 2023; Jatau & Maza, 2023) and reinforce the explanatory value of social movement theory in understanding the mechanics of religious-political influence.

Despite providing valuable insights, the study has several limitations. First, it relies primarily on qualitative data and purposive sampling, which may limit the generalisability of findings across all religious movements in Nigeria. Second, some regions, particularly areas affected by insecurity or insurgency, were less accessible, potentially restricting the breadth of data collection. Third, the study focused on the period 2010–2025; earlier historical dynamics and long-term trends may not be fully captured. Finally, while digital platforms were analyzed, rapidly evolving online ecosystems may mean that some emerging trends in religious-political communication were not fully explored.

Future research could address these limitations by adopting mixed-method approaches, combining large-scale surveys with in-depth qualitative work to enhance generalisability. Comparative studies across African multi-ethnic societies would provide insights into cross-national patterns of religious political mobilization. Additionally, longitudinal research tracing how digital media transforms religious-political influence over time would be valuable. Studies could also explore the intersection of youth engagement, gender, and religious mobilisation, given their increasing role in shaping political discourse.

Finally, more focused investigations into institutional mechanisms that successfully mediate religion-politics tensions could inform policy frameworks for enhancing social cohesion and democratic governance.

Policy Recommendations

The following policy recommendations were reached:

1. There is a need to encourage collaboration between government and religious movements to promote civic awareness, voter education, and peaceful participation in democratic processes across all ethnic groups.
2. There is a need to develop clear guidelines to ensure that religious endorsements and political mobilization respect constitutional principles, prevent bias, and avoid inflaming inter-ethnic tensions.
3. Supporting training for religious organization on responsible use of social media for political engagement, ensuring accurate information dissemination while mitigating misinformation and popularization.
4. Promotion of institutionalized interfaith forums where religious leaders can mediate conflicts, foster national cohesion, and advise policymakers on socially inclusive governance.

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